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Tulsi: A Sacred Medicinal Plant

**Dr Swati Chaurasia*

Our ancestors linked various God and Goddess with several plants having medicinal, aesthetic and spiritual qualities for their conservation. Tulsi is one such sacred plant. This plant has been well documented for its therapeutic potential and is used in variety of ceremonies in various ways throughout the year. Tulsi has innumerable medicinal applications ranging from treating coughs and colds effectively to rendering poisoning inactive. It has also been shown to detoxify the environment and purify air. This paper reviews various therapeutic potentials of Tulsi plant.

The Tulsi plant is regarded as the holiest of all plants by Hindus. In Sanskrit Tulsi means “matchless one”^[1]. Within Ayurveda, Tulsi is known as “The Incomparable One”, “The Queen of Herbs” and considered an “elixir of life”. Tulsi is worshipped by Hindus as the avatar of goddess Lakshmi. It is also known as Vishnupriya (the beloved of Vishnu) and is regarded by Hindus as a consort of the god Vishnu. Its associated religious festival is “Tulsi Vivah” which is the ceremonial marriage of the Tulsi with Lord Vishnu. This festival is helpful in removing obstacle if delay in marriage^[2]. Tulsi is renowned for its religious and spiritual sanctity, as well as for its important medicinal role in the traditional Ayurvedic, Siddha, Greek, Roman and Unani systems of medicine^[3].

Holy basil, or *tulasi* (*Ocimum sanctum*), is an aromatic plant in the family Lamiaceae which is native to the Indian subcontinent and widespread as a cultivated plant throughout the Southeast Asian tropics. Tulsi is cultivated as

it has religious and medicinal value. It is a bushy perennial plant, usually cultivated annually from seed, although it can also be propagated from tip or root cuttings. It is usually planted immediately after the rainy season ends. It is an erect, many branched subshrub, 30–60 cm tall with herbaceous, hairy, erect, quadrangular stems and simple, opposite decussate green or purple leaves that are strongly scented. Leaves have petioles and are ovate, up to 5 cm long, usually slightly serrated with unicostate reticulate venation. Inflorescence is verticillaster. The flowers are pedicillate, complete, hermaphrodite, zygomorphic, hypogynous, purplish and pentamerous. Fruits are schizocarpic (carcerulus), consisting of four nutlets. There are two types of tulsi worshipped in Hinduism: “Rama Tulsi” has light green leaves and is larger in size; “Shyama Tulsi” has dark green leaves. Both have similar constituents^[4].

According to Vaishnavas, it is believed in Puranas that during Samudra Manthana when the

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gods win the ocean-churning against asuras, Dhanvantari comes up from the ocean with Amrita in hand for the gods. Dhanvantari (the divine medico) sheds happy tears and when the first drop falls in Amrita it forms Tulsi. Vaishnavas traditionally use *japa malas* made from *tulasi* stems or roots, which are an important symbol of initiation. *Tulsi malas* are considered to be auspicious for the wearer, and believed to put them under the protection of Hanuman. It even is said to ward off the messengers of Yama, the ruler of the dead, who will not enter a house containing a sprig of Tulsi. This is also one of the reasons why devotees wear the Tulsi as neck beads. When death occurs, the funeral pyre should be constructed of Tulsi, palasha, and sandal-wood. Everything of the Tulsi plant, leaves, flowers, fruits, roots, twigs and even the soil around her is holy. The soul of a dead one whose dead body is cremated using Tulsi twigs for firewood would attain a permanent place in Vishnuloka [the spiritual abode]. Even he who has done a crore of sins would attain *moksha* [liberation] if at the time of cremating his dead body a piece of Tulsi twig is placed at the bottom of the funeral pyre.

The Tulsi plant also possesses curative properties and is said to be an antidote to snake-venom. For centuries, the dried leaves have been mixed with stored grains to repel insects. It destroys mosquitoes and other pests and purifies the air^[5,6]. Tulsi leaves added to drinking water or foodstuff is able purify it and also kills germs present in it^[7].

Tulsi is mentioned in the Charaka Samhita, an ancient Ayurvedic text. *Tulsi* is considered to be an adaptogen, balancing different processes in the body and helpful for adapting to stress. Tulsi has been used in India for more than 5,000 years in Ayurvedic medicine. The herb has

been shown to have numerous beneficial effects: pharmacological^[8], anti-microbial^[9,10,11], insecticidal^[12], nematicidal^[13], anti-fungal^[14], anti-protozoal^[15], anti-helminthic^[16], anti-convulsant^[17], immunomodulator^[18], anti-stress/adaptogenic^[19,20], anti-inflammatory^[21], anti-diabetic^[22], anti-ulcerogenic^[23], antihypertensive^[24], anti-spasmodic^[25], antioxidant^[26,27], radioprotective^[28,29] and more. Tulsi contains Vitamin A and C, Calcium, Zinc and Iron. It also has chlorophyll and other phytonutrients. Deficiency of these nutrients has been associated with variety of oral diseases^[30]. *Ocimum sanctum L.* has also got antifertility effect^[31]. Tulsi also shows some promise for protection from hyperacidity^[32] and cataracts^[33]. Tulsi is used as antiasthmatic and antikaphic drugs. It is also used in treatment of fever, bronchitis, arthritis, etc.^[1]

Each part of the plant has therapeutic value^[34]. The leaves of the Tulsi are particularly useful. They strengthen the stomach and induce copious perspiration. The leaves also cure various types of fevers. They are used for a nerve tonic and as an ingredient in many cough syrups. Chewing Tulsi leaves relieves coughs and flu. Extracts of the leaves help to decrease mental stress, eventually reducing blood pressure.

Tulsi also cures cardiac diseases, reduces blood cholesterol, and relieves diarrhoea and vomiting in children. It is used to treat mouth infections, skin disorders, eye disorders, teeth disorders, and headaches. It has been also recommended for use as a hand sanitizer, mouthwash, wound healing and preservation of food^[35].

The Tulsi plant is regarded as holiest of all plants. It wards off evil, cure diseases and brings fresh air in life. For this reason many people in India revere tulsi as sacred plant and grow it in front of their houses.

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